

IMPROVING READING SKILLS BY MODIFYING THEM ACCORDING TO THE LEVEL AND NEEDS OF LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Qualities of study skills and ways to improve them In order to fully fulfill and implement the program requirements, the first of all, it is necessary to acquire and improve reading skills correctly and carefully. Reading skills are formed in the process of teaching literacy and improve in the next stages of education.

The qualities of reading skills include reading the text of an artistic work correctly, quickly, consciously and expressively. Students' reading skills are formed and improved in reading classes. The qualities of reading skills are interrelated, the main of which is conscious reading: the student reads the text quickly and correctly, does not read it with understanding, or reads it quickly. as a result, if others do not understand the content of the text, if they read correctly, if they read too slowly, if they do not pay attention to the pauses between speech units, then the idea expressed in the text will not be understood. Reading at a certain speed and correctly serves conscious reading; correct, quick and conscious reading is the basis of expressive reading.

Acquiring reading skills is an important condition for successfully mastering all subjects taught at school. Reading is the main type of activity, which creates a great opportunity for students to develop ideologically, politically, intellectually, aesthetically and verbally. This process requires systematic and purposeful work on the growth and improvement of reading skills.

INTRODUCTION

Reading plays an important role in education, upbringing and human development. Reading is the main tool of primary school, it affects the intellectual and moral development of students, develops and strengthens their thinking and interest, the child's speech and creative abilities. Reading is a means of self-education and self-development, which has a general educational character and is used by a student in learning all academic subjects. is a set of skills. If the

theater begins with a hanger, the ways of learning and self-education begin with the ability to read.

That formation of correct, fluent and conscious reading skills is one of the urgent problems of primary school. Poor reading, underestimated relative to optimal speed, leads to almost all problems of the school system, ie. Reading speed is an important factor affecting learning outcomes, maintaining interest, persistence, and enjoyment of reading. It is important for the teacher to know the psychological basis of reading speed. Phlegmatic and melancholic people gradually increase their reading speed. Here you need to be patient and respect the student's success. There are 4-5 such children in the class. Their reading speed may be slower than others. For the same, reading speed should match and exceed the speed of conversational speech, including accuracy, awareness and expressiveness of reading.

The technical side of reading lessons should be combined with the artistic side. I believe that technical exercises on the formation of reading skills should be transferred to a separate, short stage of the lesson, and for this, texts and other speech materials that do not have great artistic value should be selected, compiled, and the main part should be devoted. time to study and work, as on a work of art.

It would be appropriate if various exercises aimed at improving reading technique skills were used in the lessons.

Below we will mention some of them.

- Reading after the speaker. (Contributes to the development of articulation and the ability to read words continuously.)
- Study in pairs. (It teaches the ability to divide attention and has a positive effect on improving the reading quality of weak students.)
- Reading without taking eyes off the text. (It teaches the student to quickly manage the text, helps to develop short-term memory, the ability to divide attention.)
- A lot of reading. (Contributes to the accumulation of visual images of words in the student's memory, teaches correct reading at the stage of learning to read and write).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It should be remembered that reading is a complex psychophysiological process.

There are three main points to keep in mind while reading:

1. Understanding these words - being able to write the words they denote.
2. Understanding the content related to the read words.
3. Evaluation of what has been read - the ability not only to read a book, but also to be critical of its content. In children, this process, as you know, is not always observed.

Reading skill is an automated skill of reciting printed text aloud, which involves understanding the idea of the perceived work and developing one's own attitude to what is being read. "Reflective reading" based on excellent reading skills becomes a means of introducing the child to cultural traditions, immersing himself in the world of literature, and forming his personality.

RESULTS

There are several effective methods for organizing the reading technique, and the most important component that affects its other aspects is the reading method. Here are five key ways to get better results:

- 1) method of reading letter by letter;
- 2) stressed syllables and stressed words
- 3) cases with smooth articulation and free pronunciation;
- 4) a smooth syllable with a single reading of individual words;
- 5) reading whole words and phrases.

Great attention should be paid to vocabulary work in reading lessons. Students know how to use the dictionary and find an explanation for this or that difficult word. Students are very interested in working on figurative expressions, epithets, comparisons. Students love choosing synonyms and antonyms for words. They know these concepts and are very good at completing tasks.

CONCLUSION

Having studied the psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, we came to the following conclusion: the purpose of literary education at school is "to form the spiritual world of a person, to develop a love for reading, to form his inner need. for the continuous spiritual and moral improvement of a person, it allows them to realize and realize their personal potential. Thus, the standard focuses on preparing a competent reader and forming a spiritually mature person. Nowadays, interest in reading literature is declining dramatically due to many reasons. Therefore, the most important task of literature classes is to educate a creative, talented, aesthetically educated reader.

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